

THE USE OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE TEACHING OF THE IRON AGE IN UZBEKISTAN

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8052405>

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Abstract

This article presents the development of pedagogical technology and application in Uzbekistan.

Key words

Technology, development of scientific technologies, pedagogical technology, pedagogical process, pedagogical science.

The concept of "technology" has received its own development with possible information systems and their accumulation in various technological, scientific and pedagogical processes. In pedagogical science, a new concept appeared that needed to be felt - pedagogical technology. The direction of coverage in the mid-sixties of the twentieth century with other countries, and at that time the distribution went to all developed countries of the globe.

Achieving the quality of education in all places involves providing the pedagogical process with up-to-date information, the use of inter-research and forms of education, the use of modern scientific technologies, the integration of disciplinary programs, the use of information and innovative technologies.

It is possible to classify pedagogical technologies according to the following criteria: needs, sizes, forms, etc.

At present, many pedagogical technologies are already used not only in the educational process of an educational institution, all this allows us to say that such a development of education as technologization makes the learning process more efficient and of high quality.

The main difference between pedagogical technology and any other is that it is highly effective in learning, taking into account the interest and frequency of

motivation of students. In the course of the study, methods of scientific knowledge were used, such as analysis and synthesis, systematization and concretization, the study of documents and literature, modeling and design, etc.

Pedagogical technologies are understood as a number of directed actions to achieve the goals of training and education, within the framework of a comprehensive pedagogical process for a teacher.

Taking into account the fact that the pedagogical process is a complex system built on the development of research, we propose to say that pedagogical technology is a set of research data used by the teacher. This shows the difference between pedagogical technology and teaching methodology, the essence of which is the collection of techniques and teaching methods, regardless of the subject of activity. Thus, the pedagogical goal will be effectively achieved if adequate pedagogical technology is used, which will be competently implemented by the teacher.

Pedagogical technologies can be classified into technologies of the educational process and technologies of the educational process. Significant manifestations of various types of pedagogical technologies are:

- pedagogical technology is solved taking into account a specific pedagogical idea, which depends on the goals and objectives of the educational process;
- at the technological stages of describing the characteristics of the installation, which are aimed at a specific result, and with their implementation, the setting of operations and actions is carried out, as well as the communicative component of this process is built;
- Any pedagogical technology should be easily reproducible among teachers, and also has elements of variability so that all students can get learning results.

All this, as well as changes at the level of the socio-economic and scientific-technical process, led to the prospect of professional and pedagogical education, rethinking of theoretical approaches and extensive practice of educational institutions.

Pedagogical science is constantly in search of educational technologies and methods that would allow achieving educational results in working with students, and also constantly consume the existing base.

REFERENCES:

1. Cyplakova S. A., Krivonogova A. S. Metody issledovaniya problem professional'nogo obrazivaniya // Vestnik Mininskogo universiteta. 2017. № 1 (18). 5 p.
2. Markova S. M., Narkoziev A. K. Politeoreticheskie osnovy professional'no-pedagogicheskogo obrazovaniya // Vestnik Mininskogo universiteta. 2016. № 3 (16). 2 p.
3. Pedagogicheskiy enciklopedicheskiy slovar' / gl. red. B. M. Bim-Bad. - M.: Bol'shaya Rossiyskaya encyclopedia, 2008. – 528 p.